

Smarandache Fuzzy Strong Ideal and Smarandache Fuzzy n-Fold Strong Ideal of a BH-Algebra

Shahrezad Jasim Mohammed

Abstract: In this paper, we define the concepts of a Q-Smarandache n-fold strong ideal and a Q-Smarandache fuzzy (strong, n-fold strong) ideal of a BH-algebra. Also, we study some properties of these fuzzy ideals

Keywords: BCK-algebra, BCI/BCH-algebras, BH-algebra, Smarandache BH-algebra, Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal.

1. Introduction

In 1965, L. A. Zadeh introduced the notion of a fuzzy subset of a set as a method for representing uncertainty in real physical world [7]. In 1991, O. G. Xi applied the concept of fuzzy sets to the BCK-algebras [8]. In 1993, Y. B. Jun introduced the notion of closed fuzzy ideals in BCI-algebras [11]. In 1999, Y. B. Jun introduced the notion of fuzzy closed ideal in BCH-algebras [13]. In 2001, Q. Zhang, E. H. Roh and Y. B. Jun studied the fuzzy theory in a BH-algebra [10]. In 2006, C. H. Park introduced the notion of an interval valued fuzzy BH-algebra in a BH-algebra [2]. In 2009, A. B. Saeid and A. Namdar, introduced the notion of a Smarandache BCH-algebra and Q-Smarandache ideal of a Smarandache BCH-algebra [1]. In 2012, H. H. Abbass introduced the notion of a Q-Smarandache fuzzy closed ideal with respect to an element of a Smarandache BCH-algebra [5]. In the same year, E. M. Kim and S. S. Ahn defined the notion of a fuzzy (n-fold strong) ideal of a BH-algebra [3]. In 2013, E. M. Kim and S. S. Ahn defined the notion of a fuzzy (strong) ideal of a BH-algebra [4]. In the same year, H. H. Abbass and S. J. Mohammed introduced the Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal with respect to an element of a BH-algebra [6]. In this paper, we define the concepts of Q-Smarandache n-fold strong ideal and a Q-Smarandache fuzzy (strong, n-fold strong) ideal of a Smarandache BH-algebra. Also, we study some properties of these fuzzy ideals

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we give some basic concept about a BCK-algebra, a BCI-algebra, a BH-algebra, a BH*-algebra, a normal BH-algebra, fuzzy strong ideal, fuzzy n-fold strong ideal, a Smarandache BH-algebra, (Q-Smarandache ideal, Q-Smarandache fuzzy closed ideal, Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal and Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of BH-algebra

Definition 1 (see[11]). A BCI-algebra is an algebra $(X, *, 0)$, where X is a nonempty set, $*$ is a binary operation and 0 is a constant, satisfying the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- i. $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$, ii. $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- iii. $x * x = 0$,
- iv. $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$.

Definition 2 (see [8]). A BCK-algebra is a BCI-algebra satisfying the axiom

v. $0 * x = 0$ for all $x \in X$.

Definition 3 (see[9]). A BH-algebra is a nonempty set X with a constant 0 and a binary operation $*$ satisfying the following conditions: i. $x * x = 0, \forall x \in X$

- ii. $x * 0 = x, \forall x \in X$.
- iii. $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 4 (see[4]). A BH-algebra X is called a BH*-algebra if $(x * y) * x = 0$ for all $x, y \in X$

Definition 5 (see[9]). A BH-algebra X is said to be a normal BH-algebra if it satisfies the following condition:

- i. $0 * (x * y) = (0 * x) * (0 * y), \forall x, y \in X$.
- ii. $(x * y) * x = 0 * y, \forall x, y \in X$.
- iii. $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0, \forall x, y \in X$.

Definition 6 (see[5]). Let X be a BH-algebra. Then the set $X_+ = \{x \in X : 0 * x = 0\}$ is called the BCA-part of X .

Remark 1 (see[6]). Let X and Y be BH-algebras. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called a homomorphism if $f(x * y) = f(x) * f(y)$ for all $x, y \in X$. A homomorphism f is called a monomorphism (resp., epimorphism) if it is injective (resp., surjective). For any homomorphism $f : X \rightarrow Y$, the set $\{x \in X : f(x) = 0\}$ is called the kernel of f , denoted by $\text{Ker}(f)$, and the set $\{f(x) : x \in X\}$ is called the image of f , denoted by $\text{Im}(f)$. Notice that $f(0) = 0$ for all homomorphism f .

Definition 7 (see[3]). Let X be a BH-algebra and n be a positive integer. A nonempty subset I of X is called a n-fold strong ideal of X if it satisfies: i. $0 \in I$, ii. $\forall y \in I$ and $(x * y) * z^n \in I \Rightarrow x * z^n \in I, \forall x, z \in X$.

Definition 8 (see[6]). A Smarandache BH-algebra is defined to be a BH-algebra X in which there exists a proper subset Q of X such that

- i. $0 \in Q$ and $|Q| \geq 2$.
- ii. Q is a BCK-algebra under the operation of X .

Definition 9 (see[6]). Let X be a Smarandache BH-algebra. A nonempty subset I of X is called a Smarandache strong ideal of X related to Q (or briefly, Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X) if it satisfies: i. $0 \in I$, ii. $\forall y \in I$ and $(x * y) * z \in I \Rightarrow x * z \in I, \forall x, z \in Q$.

Definition 10(see[7]). Let μ be a fuzzy set in X , for all $t \in [0,1]$. The set $\mu_t = \{x \in X, \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called a **level subset of μ** .

Definition 11(see [4]). Let A and B be any two sets, μ be any fuzzy set in A and $f: A \rightarrow B$ be any function. Set $f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in A | f(x) = y\}$ for $y \in B$. The fuzzy set v in B defined by $v(y) = \begin{cases} \sup\{\mu(x) | x \in f^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ for all $y \in B$, is called the **image** of μ under f and is denoted by $f(\mu)$.

Definition 12(see [4]). Let A and B be any two sets, $f: A \rightarrow B$ be any function and v be any fuzzy set in $f(A)$. The fuzzy set μ in A defined by: $\mu(x) = v(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$ is called the **preimage** of v under f and is denoted by $f^{-1}(v)$.

Definition 13(see[4]). A fuzzy set μ in a BH-algebra X is called a fuzzy strong ideal of X if i. For all $x \in X, \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.
 ii. $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}, \forall x, y \in X$.

Definition 14(see[5]). A fuzzy set μ in a BH-algebra X is called a fuzzy n -fold strong ideal of X if i. For all $x \in X, (0) \geq \mu(x)$.
 ii. $\mu(x * z^n) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z^n); \mu(y)\}, \forall x, y \in X$.

Definition 15(see [6]). A fuzzy subset μ of a Smarandache BH-algebra X is said to be a **Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal** if and only if :

- i. For all $x \in X, \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.
 - ii. For all $x \in Q, y \in X, \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$.
- Is said to be **closed** if $(0 * x) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Definition 16(see[6]). Let X be a Smarandache BH-algebra and μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . Then μ is called a **Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal** if $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}, \forall x, y \in X$.

Proposition 1(see[6]). Let X be a BH*-algebra, and μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal. Then
 i. μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy closed ideal of X .
 ii. μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal of X , if $X * X / \{0\} \subseteq Q$

3. The Main Results

In this paper, we give the concepts a Q-Smarandache n -fold strong ideal and a Q-Smarandache fuzzy (strong, n -fold strong) ideal of a BH- algebra. Also, we give some properties of these fuzzy ideals

Definition 1. A fuzzy subset of a BH-algebra X is called a **Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal**, iff i. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X$
 ii. $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}, \forall x, z \in Q$.

Example 1: The set $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ with the following operation table

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	2	2
1	1	0	1	2
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

is a BH-algebra $Q = \{0,1\}$ is a BCK-algebra. Then $(X, *, 0)$ is a Smarandache BH-algebra. The fuzzy set μ which is defined by:

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.5 & x = 0,3 \\ 0.4 & x = 1,2 \end{cases}$$

is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal, since: i. $\mu(0) = 0.5 \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X$, ii. $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}, \forall x, z \in Q$.

But the fuzzy set $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.5 & x = 0,2,3 \\ 0.4 & x = 1 \end{cases}$

is not a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal since $\mu(1 * 0) = \mu(1) = 0.4 < \min\{\mu(1 * 3) * 0, \mu(3)\} = 0.5$

Proposition 1. Every Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of a Smarandache BH-algebra X is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof : Let μ be a fuzzy strong ideal of X .

- i. Let $x \in X \Rightarrow (0) \geq \mu(x)$.

[By definition 1(i)]

- ii. let $x, z \in X$ and $y \in X \Rightarrow x, z \in Q \Rightarrow \mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}$

[By definition 1(ii)]

When $z=0 \Rightarrow \mu(x * 0) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * 0), \mu(y)\} \Rightarrow \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$

$\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Proposition 2. Let Q_1 and Q_2 be a BCK-algebras contained in a Smarandache BH- algebra X and $Q_1 \subseteq Q_2$. Let μ be Q_2 -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X then μ is a Q_1 -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X .

Proof : Let μ be a Q_2 -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X .

- i. Let $x \in X \Rightarrow \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.

[Since μ is a Q_2 -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. By definition 1(i)]

- ii. Let $x, z \in Q_1, y \in X \Rightarrow x, z \in Q_2$

$\Rightarrow \mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}$

[Since μ is a Q_2 -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. By definition 1(ii)]

$\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q_1 -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X . ■

Proposition 3. Every fuzzy strong ideal of a Smarandache BH-algebra X is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X .

Proof : Let μ be a fuzzy strong ideal of X .

- i. Let $x \in X \Rightarrow \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.

[By definition 13(i)]

- ii. let $x, z \in X$ and $y \in X \Rightarrow x, z \in Q$

$\Rightarrow \mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}$

[By definition 13(ii)]

$\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X . ■

Theorem 1. Let X be Smarandache BH-algebra and let μ be a fuzzy set. Then μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal if and only if $v(x) = \mu(x) / \mu(0)$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal.

Proof: Let μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal,

1) $v(0) = \mu(0) / \mu(0) \Rightarrow v(0) = 1$

$\Rightarrow v(0) \geq v(x) \forall x \in X$

2) $v(x*z) = \mu(x*z) / \mu(0)$
 $\geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\} / \mu(0)$
 [Since μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. .By definition1(ii)]
 $\geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z) / \mu(0), \mu(y) / \mu(0)\}$
 $\geq \min\{v((x*y)*z), v(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow v(x*z) \geq \min\{v((x*y)*z), v(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow v$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. **Conversely.** Let v be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal.
 i. $\mu(0) = v(0) \cdot \mu(0) \Rightarrow \mu(0) \geq v(x) \cdot \mu(0)$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \quad \forall x \in X$
 ii. $\mu(x*z) = v(x*z) \cdot \mu(0) \geq \min\{v(x*(y*z)), v(y)\} \cdot \mu(0)$
 [Since μ' is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal. By definition1(i)]
 $\geq \min\{v((x*y)*z) \cdot \mu(0), v(y) \cdot \mu(0)\}$
 $\geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. ■

Proposition 4. Let X be a BH*-algebra, and μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. Then
 i. μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy closed ideal of X .
 ii. μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal of X , if $X*X/\{0\} \subseteq Q$.

Proof : Let μ be a fuzzy strong ideal of X .
 [By Proposition 1]
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X .
 i. $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy closed ideal of X . [By proposition 1]
 ii. Let $x, y \in X \Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal of X .
 [By proposition 1]. ■

Theorem 2. Let A be a non-empty subset of a Q-Smarandache BH-algebra X and let μ be a fuzzy set in X defined by:

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} \alpha_1 & x \in Q \\ \alpha_2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$
 where $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2$ in $[0, 1]$. Then μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal X

Proof : Let μ be a fuzzy set of X .
 i. $0 \in Q \Rightarrow \mu(0) = \alpha_1. \Rightarrow \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ [Since $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2$]
 ii. let $x, z \in Q$ and $y \in X \Rightarrow x*z \in Q$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x*z) = \alpha_1$
 Then we have for cases.

Case1 If $((x*y)*z) = \alpha_1$ and $\mu(y) = \alpha_1$
 $\Rightarrow \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\} = \alpha_1$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x*z) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$

Case2 If $((x*y)*z) = \alpha_2$ and $\mu(y) = \alpha_1$
 $\Rightarrow \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\} = \alpha_2$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x*y) = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$

Case3 If $((x*y)*z) = \alpha_1$ and $\mu(y) = \alpha_2$
 $\Rightarrow \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\} = \alpha_2$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x*y) = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$

Case3 If $((x*y)*z) = \alpha_2$ and $\mu(y) = \alpha_2$
 $\Rightarrow \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\} = \alpha_2$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x*y) = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X . ■

Theorem 3. Let X be BH-algebra and let μ be a fuzzy set. Then μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal if and only if $\mu'(x) = \mu(x) + 1 - \mu(0)$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal.

Proof: Let μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal,
 i. $\mu(0) = \mu(0) + 1 - \mu(0) \Rightarrow \mu'(0) = 1$
 $\Rightarrow \mu'(0) \geq \mu'(x) \quad \forall x \in X$
 ii. $\mu(x*z) = \mu(x*z) + 1 - \mu(0)$
 $\geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\} + 1 - \mu(0)$ [Since μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. .By definition1]
 $\geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z) + 1 - \mu(0), \mu(y) + 1 - \mu(0)\} \geq \min\{\mu'((x*y)*z), \mu'(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu'(x*z) \geq \min\{\mu'((x*y)*z), \mu'(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu'$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal.

Conversely Let μ' be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal.
 1) $\mu'(0) = \mu'(0) - 1 + \mu(0) \Rightarrow \mu(0) \geq \mu'(x) - 1 + \mu(0) \Rightarrow \mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \quad \forall x \in X$
 2) $\mu(x*z) = \mu'(x*z) - 1 + \mu(0)$
 $\geq \min\{\mu'((x*y)*z), \mu'(y)\} - 1 + \mu(0)$ [Since μ' is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. By definition1]
 $\geq \min\{\mu'((x*y)*z) - 1 + \mu(0), \mu'(y) - 1 + \mu(0)\}$
 $\geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal. ■

Theorem4. Let X be a Smarandache BH-algebra such that $X = X_+$ and μ be a Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X . Then μ is a Q-Smarandache closed ideal of X .

Proof : Let μ be a Q-Smarandache strong ideal $\Rightarrow \mu I$ is a Q-Smarandache ideal of X . [By proposition 1]
 Now, let $x \in I$
 $\Rightarrow (0*x) = \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ [By definition 6]
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache closed ideal of X . ■

Proposition5. Let X be a Smarandache normal BH-algebra such that $X = X_+$ and let μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal such that $x*y \in Q, \forall x, y \in X$ and $y \neq 0$. Then μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal of X .

Proof: Let μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X .
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . [By remark3]
 Now, let $x, y \in X \Rightarrow x*y \in Q$
 [Since $x*y \in Q, \forall x, y \in X$]
 We have
 $\mu(x*y) = \mu((x*y)*0) \geq \min\{\mu(((x*y)*x)*0), \mu(x)\}$ [By definition 3(ii)]
 $= \min\{\mu((x*y)*x), \mu(x)\}$ [By definition 3(ii)] = $\min\{\mu(0*y), \mu(x)\}$ [By definition 5(ii)]
 $= \min\{\mu(0), \mu(x)\} = \mu(x)$
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x*y) \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(x)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal. ■

Proposition 6. Let X be a normal BH-algebra such that $X*X/\{0\} \subseteq Q$. Then every Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal and closed of X is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal of X .

Proof : Let μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X .

$\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X. [By proposition1]
 Now, let $x, y \in X. \Rightarrow x*y \in Q$ [Since $X*X \setminus \{0\} \subseteq Q$]
 $\Rightarrow \mu(x*y) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*x)*0, \mu(x)\}$ [By definition1]
 $= \min\{\mu(0*y), \mu(x)\}$ [By definition 5(ii)]
 $\geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(x)\}$ [By definition14]
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy completely closed ideal of X.

Remark 1. Let μ be a fuzzy set of a Smarandache BH-algebra X and $w \in X$. The set $\{x \in X: (w) \leq \mu(x)\}$ is denoted by $\uparrow \mu(w)$.

Theorem 5. Let X be a Smarandache BH-algebra, $w \in X$ and μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X. Then $\uparrow(w)$ is a Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X.

Proof : Let μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X. To prove that $\uparrow(w)$ is a Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X.

1) Let $x \in \uparrow(w) \Rightarrow \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ [By definition 1(i)]

$\Rightarrow (0) \geq \mu(w) \Rightarrow 0 \in \uparrow \mu(w)$

2) Let $x, z \in Q, y \in \uparrow \mu(w)$ and $(x*y)*z \in \uparrow \mu(w)$.

$\Rightarrow (w) \leq \mu(y)$ and $\mu(w) \leq \mu((x*y)*z)$

$\Rightarrow (w) \leq \min\{\mu(y), \mu((x*y)*z)\}$

But $\mu(x*z) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$ [By definition 1(ii)]

$\Rightarrow (w) \leq \mu(x*z) \Rightarrow x*z \in \uparrow \mu(w)$

$\Rightarrow \uparrow(w)$ is a Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X. ■

Corollary 1. Let X be a Smarandache BH-algebra. Then μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X if and only if μ_t is a Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X, for all $t \in [0, \sup_{x \in X} \mu(x)]$

Proof : Let $t \in [0, \sup_{x \in X} \mu(x)]$. To prove that μ_t is a Q-

Smarandache strong ideal of X. Since μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X.

Now, let $y \in \mu_t$ and $x*(y*z) \in \mu_t \Rightarrow \mu(y) \geq t$ and $\mu((x*y)*z) \geq t$.

To prove that $x*z \in \mu_t$

We have $\mu(x*z) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$ [By definition 1]

Since $((x*y)*z) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t \Rightarrow \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\} \geq t$

$\Rightarrow \mu(x*z) \geq t \Rightarrow x*z \in \mu_t$

$\Rightarrow \mu_t$ is a Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X.

Conversely,

To prove that μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X.

Since μ_t is a Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X.

Let $t = \sup_{x \in X} \mu(x), x, z \in Q$ and $(x*y)*z, y \in \mu_t$

$\Rightarrow x*z \in \mu_t$ [By definition9]

$\Rightarrow \mu(x*z) \geq t \Rightarrow \mu(x*z) = t$ [Since $t = \sup_{x \in X} \mu(x)$]

Similarly, $((x*y)*z) = t$ and $\mu(y) = t$

$\Rightarrow t = \min\{((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$

$\Rightarrow \mu(x*z) \geq \min\{((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$

$\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X. ■

Proposition 7 . Let $f : (X, *, 0) \rightarrow (Y, *', 0')$ be a Smarandache BH-epimorphism. If μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X, then $f(\mu)$ is a $f(Q)$ -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of Y.

Proof : Let μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X.

i. Let $y \in f(\mu)$ such that $y = f(x)$.

$(f(\mu))(0') = \sup\{\mu(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(0')\}$

$= (0) \geq \mu(x)$ [By definition 1(i)]

$= (f(\mu))(f(x))$

$= (f(\mu))(y) \Rightarrow (f(\mu))(0') \geq (f(\mu))(y)$

ii. Let $y_1, y_3 \in f(Q), y_2 \in Y$, there exists $x_1, x_3 \in Q$ and $x_2 \in X$ such that $y_1 = f(x_1), y_3 = f(x_3)$ and $y_2 = f(x_2) \Rightarrow (f(\mu))(y_1 * y_3) = \sup\{\mu(x_1 * x_3) \mid x \in f^{-1}(y_1 * y_3)\}$

$(f(\mu))(y_1 * y_3) \geq (x_1 * x_3) \geq \min\{\mu((x_1 * x_2) * x_3), \mu(x_2)\}$ [By definition 1(ii)]

$= \min\{(f(\mu))(f((x_1 * x_2) * x_3)), (f(\mu))(x_2)\} = \min\{(f(\mu))((x_1) *' f(x_2)) *' f(x_3), (f(\mu))(f(x_2))\} = \min\{(f(\mu))(y_1 *' y_2) *' y_3, (f(\mu))(y_2)\}$

$\Rightarrow (f(\mu))(y_1) \geq \min\{(f(\mu))((y_1 *' y_2) *' y_3), (f(\mu))(y_2)\}$

$\Rightarrow f(\mu)$ is a $f(Q)$ -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of Y. ■

Theorem 6. Let $f : (X, *, 0) \rightarrow (Y, *', 0')$ be a Smarandache BH-epimorphism. If μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X, then $f^{-1}(v)$ is a $f^{-1}(Q)$ -Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of Y

Proof : i. Let $x \in X$. Since $f(x) \in Y$ and v is a Q-Smarandache strong fuzzy ideal of Y.

$(f^{-1}(v))(0) = v(f(0)) = v(0') \geq v(f(x)) = (f^{-1}(v))(x)$

ii. Let $x \in f^{-1}(Q), y \in X$.

$f^{-1}(v)(x * z) = (f(x * z))$ [By definition 12]

$\geq \min\{v(f(x) *' f(y)) *' f(z), v(f(y))\}$ [By remark 1]

$= \min\{v(f((x * y) * z)), v(f(y))\}$

$\Rightarrow f^{-1}(v)(x) \geq \min\{f^{-1}(v)((x * y) * z), f^{-1}(v)(y)\}$ [By definition 1]

$\Rightarrow f^{-1}(v)$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X. ■

Definition 2. Let X be a Smarandache BH-algebra and n be a positive integer. A nonempty subset I of X is called a **Smarandache-fold strong ideal of X related to Q** (or briefly, **Q-Smarandache-fold strong ideal of X**) if it satisfies: i. $0 \in I$, ii. $\forall y \in I$ and $(x * y) * z^n \in I \Rightarrow x * z \in I, \forall x, z \in Q$.

Example 2. Consider the set $I = \{0, 3\}$ in example 1 is a Q-Smarandache-fold strong ideal of X. But the set $I = \{0, 2, 3\}$ is not a Q-Smarandache-fold strong ideal since $(1 * 3) * 0^2 = 2 \in I$, but $1 * 0^2 = 1 \notin I$.

Remark 2. Every n-fold strong ideal of a Smarandache BH-algebra X is a Q-Smarandache-fold strong ideal of X.

Remark 3. Every Q-Smarandache-fold strong ideal of a Smarandache BH-algebra X is a Q-Smarandache strong ideal of X.

Remark 4. Every Q-Smarandache-fold strong ideal of a Smarandache BH-algebra X is a Q-Smarandache ideal of X.

Proposition 8 . Let X be a Smarandache BH-algebra. Then every Q-Smarandache-fold strong ideal which is contained in Q is a Q-Smarandache completely closed ideal of X.

Proof : Let I be a Q-Smarandache-fold strong ideal of X $\Rightarrow I$ is a Q-Smarandache ideal of X. [By remark 4]

Now, let $x, y \in I \Rightarrow x, y \in Q \Rightarrow x * y \in Q$ [Since $I \subseteq Q$]

Where $((x*y)*x)*0 = ((x*x)*y)*0$ [Since $(x*y)*z = (x*z)*y$.
 By definition 1(iii)]
 $= (0*y)*0$ [By definition 3(i)]
 $= 0*y$ [By definition 3(ii)]
 $= 0 \in I$ [Since $0*x=0$.By definition 2(v)]
 $\Rightarrow ((x*y)*x)*0^n \in I$ and $x \in I \Rightarrow (x*y)*0^n \in I \Rightarrow x*y \in I$ [By definition 3(ii)]
 $\Rightarrow I$ is a Q-Smarandache completely closed ideal of X. ■

Definition 3. A fuzzy subset of a Smarandache BH-algebra X and n be a positive integer is called a **Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal**, iff i. $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X$. ii. $\mu(x*z^n) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z^n), \mu(y)\}, \forall x, z \in Q$.

Example 3. Consider the fuzzy set μ which is defined by:

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.5 & x = 0, 2 \\ 0.4 & x = 1, 3 \end{cases}$$

is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal, since: i. $\mu(0) = 0.5 \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X$, ii. $\mu(x*z^1) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z^1), \mu(y)\}, \forall x, z \in Q$.

But the fuzzy set $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.5 & x = 0, 2, 3 \\ 0.4 & x = 1 \end{cases}$

is not a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal since $\mu(1*0^3) = \mu(1) = 0.4 < \min\{\mu(1*3)*0^3, \mu(3)\} = 0.5$

Remark 5. Every fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of a Smarandache BH-algebra X is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X.

Proposition 9. Every Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of a Smarandache BH-algebra X is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X.

Proof: Let μ be a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X. i. Let $x \in X \Rightarrow (0) \geq \mu(x)$. [By definition 3(i)]
 ii. let $x, z \in Q$ and $y \in X \Rightarrow \mu(x*z^n) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z^n), \mu(y)\}$ [By definition 3(ii)]
 When $n=1 \Rightarrow \mu(x*z) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z), \mu(y)\}$
 $\Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy strong ideal of X. ■

Theorem 7. Let $f: (X, *, 0) \rightarrow (Y, *', 0')$ be a Smarandache BH-epimorphism. If ν is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of Y, then $f^{-1}(\nu)$ is a $f^{-1}(Q)$ -Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X.

Proof: i. Let $x \in X$. Since $f(x) \in Y$ and ν is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of Y.

$$(f^{-1}(\nu))(0) = \nu(f(0)) = \nu(0') \geq \nu(f(x)) = (f^{-1}(\nu))(x)$$

ii. Let $x, z \in f^{-1}(Q), y \in X$.

$$f^{-1}(\nu)(x*z^n) = (f(x*z^n)) \text{ [By definition 11]}$$

$$\geq \min\{\nu(f(x) *' f(y)) *' f(z^n), \nu(f(y))\}$$

[By remark 1]

$$= \min\{\nu(f((x*y)*z^n)), \nu(f(y))\}$$

$$\Rightarrow f^{-1}(\nu)(x*z^n) \geq \min\{f^{-1}(\nu)((x*y)*z^n), f^{-1}(\nu)(y)\}$$

$\Rightarrow f^{-1}(\nu)$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X. ■

Theorem 8. Let X be Smarandache BH-algebra. If μ is a fuzzy set such that Q=

$X_\mu = \{x \in X: \mu(x) = \mu(0)\}$ and $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X$, then μ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X.

Proof: Let μ be a fuzzy set of X, such that $Q = X_\mu$ and $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X$.

i. $(0) \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X$.

ii. Let $x, z \in Q$ and $y \in X$.

$$(0) \geq \mu(y) \quad \text{and} \quad \mu(0) \geq \mu((x*y)*z^n) \text{ [Since } \mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \forall x \in X]$$

$$\Rightarrow (0) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z^n), \mu(y)\}$$

But $\mu(x*z^n) = \mu(0)$ [Since $Q = X_\mu$]

$\Rightarrow \mu(x*z^n) \geq \min\{\mu((x*y)*z^n), \mu(y)\} \Rightarrow \mu$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X. ■

Proposition 10. Let $\{\mu_\alpha: \alpha \in \lambda\}$ be a family of Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideals of a Smarandache BH-algebra X.

Then $\bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha$ is a fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X.

Proof: Let $\{\mu_\alpha: \alpha \in \lambda\}$ be a family of Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideals of X.

i. Let $x \in X$. $\bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(0) = \inf\{\mu_\alpha(0), \alpha \in \lambda\} \geq \inf\{\mu_\alpha(x), \alpha \in \lambda\}$

[Since μ_α is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold ideal, $\forall \alpha \in \lambda$. By definition 3(i)]

$$= \bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(x) \Rightarrow \bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(0) \geq \bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(x)$$

ii. Let $x, z \in Q$ and $y \in X$

$$\bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(x*z^n) = \inf\{\mu_\alpha(x*z^n), \alpha \in \lambda\} \geq \inf\{\min\{\mu_\alpha((x*y)*z^n), \mu_\alpha(y)\}, \alpha \in \lambda\}$$

[Since μ_α is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal, $\forall \alpha \in \lambda$. By definition 3(ii)] = $\min\{\inf\{\mu_\alpha((x*y)*z^n), \alpha \in \lambda\}, \inf\{\mu_\alpha(y), \alpha \in \lambda\}\}$

$$= \min\{\bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha((x*y)*z^n), \bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(y)\}$$

$$\Rightarrow \bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(x*z^n) \geq \min\{\bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha((x*y)*z^n), \bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(y)\} \Rightarrow$$

$\bigcap_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X. ■

Proposition 11. Let $\{\mu_\alpha: \alpha \in \lambda\}$ be a chain of Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideals of a Smarandache BH-algebra X.

Then $\bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X.

Proof: Let $\{\mu_\alpha: \alpha \in \lambda\}$ be a chain of Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideals of X.

i. Let $x \in X$. $\bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha(0) = \sup\{\mu_\alpha(0), \alpha \in \lambda\} \geq \sup\{\mu_\alpha(x), \alpha \in \lambda\}$

[Since μ_α is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal, $\forall \alpha \in \lambda$. By definition 3(i)]

$\Rightarrow \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_\alpha$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal, $\forall \alpha \in \lambda$. By definition 3(i)]

$$= \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}(x) \Rightarrow \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}(0) \geq \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}(x) \quad \forall x \in X .$$

ii. Let $x, z \in Q, y \in X$. $\bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}(x * z^n) = \sup\{ \mu_{\alpha}(x), \alpha \in \lambda \} \geq$

$$\sup\{ \min\{ \mu_{\alpha}((x * y) * z^n), \mu_{\alpha}(y) \}, \alpha \in \lambda \}$$

[Since μ_{α} is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal, $\forall \alpha \in \lambda$. By definition 3(ii)]

But $\{ \alpha, \alpha \in \lambda \}$ is a chain \Rightarrow there exist, $j \in \lambda$ such that $\sup\{ \min\{ \mu_{\alpha}((x * y) * z^n), \mu_{\alpha}(y) \}, \alpha \in \lambda \} = \min\{ \mu_j((x * y) * z^n), \mu_j(y) \}$

$$= \min\{ \sup\{ \mu_{\alpha}((x * y) * z^n), \alpha \in \lambda \}, \sup\{ \mu_{\alpha}(y), \alpha \in \lambda \} \}$$

$$\Rightarrow \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}(x * z^n) \geq \min\{ \mu_j((x * y) * z^n), \mu_j(y) \}$$

$$\geq \min\{ \sup\{ \mu_{\alpha}((x * y) * z^n), \alpha \in \lambda \}, \sup\{ \mu_{\alpha}(y), \alpha \in \lambda \} \} = \min\{$$

$$\bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}((x * y) * z^n), \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}(y) \}$$

$$\Rightarrow \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}(x * z^n) \geq \min\{ \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}((x * y) * z^n), \bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}(y) \} \Rightarrow$$

$\bigcup_{\alpha \in \lambda} \mu_{\alpha}$ is a Q-Smarandache fuzzy n-fold strong ideal of X.

■

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